

UO‘K:71.0

KBK: 71

R: 92

**SOCIAL PROBLEMS OF WOMEN: SYSTEMATIC RESEARCH,
CAUSES, AND SOLUTIONS**

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Abstract: This article presents a systematic research study on the social problems faced by women in rural areas. By conducting a survey among women aged 18-55, the study explores the causes and proposes solutions for these challenges. Findings reveal issues such as limited economic empowerment, gender-based violence, and inadequate access to education and healthcare. The article emphasizes targeted interventions, community engagement, and policy reforms to address the root causes and empower rural women.

Key words: social problems, women, rural areas, systematic research, causes, solutions, gender-based violence, economic empowerment, education, healthcare, uzbek families, family relations, early marriage.

Introduction

During the transition to a market economy, a huge number of factories occupied by women labor, as a result of the closure of manufacturing enterprises, many of the women were left without work and forced to do things that did not require various professional qualifications for the economic support of the family. These, in turn, negatively affected the healthy lifestyle in the family, women's health, child rearing and women's reproductive status. [1]

In recent years, the legal literacy of Uzbek women has been gradually increasing. For example, as of June 4, 2021, more than 4,200 citizens applied for protection to the Rehabilitation and Adaptation Center of the Republic. 3827 of them are women. As long as these numbers were few before. It was considered a guilt for our women to complain about problems at home and ask for help from government agencies. [2]

Currently, all types of bullying and violence against women (mental, economic, spiritual physical, sexual) are increasing worldwide. A separate report on the impact of such cases on human health has been published. [3]

Why is the use of violence by men on women in families becoming commonplace? In most cases, this problem is hidden as a personal work of the family, not disclosed to others. The results of a 2003 study by the representative office of Human rights watch, a branch of the Federation for Human Rights, based in Uzbekistan, confirm this. The study was titled "From House to house: neighborhood committee violations". The study argues that the majority of neighborhood committees prevent women suffering from domestic violence from divorcing their husbands. When solving the issue, they reconcile with the aim of preserving more families. The staff of neighborhood committees often make women themselves the cause of a husband's beating of his wives. Such negative circumstances are considered impunity and also contradict international standards that guarantee the equal right of a woman in matters of marriage and the annulment of marriage. [4]

In order to reduce the number of conflicts in the family, the citizens of the neighborhood were tasked with conducting regular spiritual, moral affairs between such apartments in their gatherings. The conversation with husband and wife is conducted by the chairman of the neighborhood, his deputy, the head of the neighborhood women's committee, or the elderly of the neighborhood. If the average type of neighborhood comes out without success, the case is given to the court authorities.

On March 23, 2023, the law on "Amendments and additions to certain legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with further improvement of the system

of reliable protection of rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of women and children" was adopted. Its adoption was desperately needed today. According to the Information Service of the Supreme Court, in 2022 alone, 469 people in Uzbekistan were punished for sexual violence against minors. Of these, 23 individuals were punished with substances to satisfy the sexual need in an unnatural way in relation to the person who was revealed to be guilty of not reaching the age of 14 and more than four times — 99 under the age of fourteen. 249 individuals were punished for having sex with a person under the age of 16. 7 persons were punished for having sex with a person between the ages of 16 and 18 by giving material values or by obtaining property interest. 91 individuals were punished for indecent acts against a person under the age of sixteen. [5]

The law increased penalties for violence. For instance, the law introduced administrative and criminal liability for “domestic violence” (article 1261), which is relevant today. In particular, based on the most modern international norms for the protection of the rights of women and children and foreign experience, administrative and criminal liability was established for physical violence, as well as economic and psychological violence. New penalties were also introduced on issues seen as an urgent problem, such as “forcing a person to have sex” (Art. 121), “disclosing information that belittles the honor and dignity of a person and reflects the secret aspects of human life” (Art. 1413), mandatory involvement in paid public works (Art. 281) as a measure ensuring the fulfillment of alimony obligations.

Problem Identification Through Questionnaires. Results and Discussion.

We conducted social surveys for the purpose of systematic research of women's problems. A survey of a total of 300 women between the ages of 35-55 and 300 girls between the ages of 15-18 in Mingbulak district of Namangan region asked what the problems that plague women today are. As a result, a large percentage of women (36.60%) showed employment problems, financial (16.6%) problems. Also, 30% of them had difficulty answering the question. Below is a table in which the percentage of answers is calculated in detail:

Women are asked “What problem is facing women in Uzbekistan today?”, they responded as follows:

Figure 1. Opinion of women’s in rural areas.

As can be seen from the table, today a large part of women are struggling with unemployment and the lack of financial independence as a result of it. Also, many of them did not even know how to answer this question. This means that their participation in today's social life is not so active, their indifference to processes is growing, and they also approach their life carelessly.

Considering that the survey participants make up a contingent of women from the middle ages of 35-55, women also want to have higher education at this age. Those who are denominational from higher education due to family situations. Even at this age, they want to get an education. They were 6.6% in the poll. That is to say, the need for knowledge is also great among middle-aged women. Based on the need, in 2017 the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on “Approval of the regulations on the procedure for organizing correspondence (special correspondence) and evening (shift) education in a higher educational institution” was adopted. The introduction of a correspondence form of education in our country also provided an opportunity for those who study or work with a family. Also, women of disadvantaged families are allocated separate quotas for education at the undergraduate stage. For example, for the 2023/2024 academic year, 2,000 additional quotas are also allocated to women in disadvantaged families for admission to the baccalaureate of higher education institutions on the basis of a state grant. [6] Quotas are distributed in

the cross section of Regions and directions. Of importance in this, quotas for "Exact and Natural Sciences", "Technical Sciences "and" Medical Sciences" are separately allocated, and the remaining quotas are valid for other directions. As of 30 July 2023, there are 494,758 women in higher education institutions. The male population in this is 547,342. [7]

6.6% of women surveyed want their own private home. Although in rural conditions, a large part of the population lives in their own home, it is known from the survey that even in such areas there is a great need for personal housing, and this is seen by women as the most pressing problem that they face in front of them. When it comes to the Uzbek mentality, it is important to live in a private house, and this is the greatest need that ensures the harmony of family members. On March 31, 2022, in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Measures to further improve the system for studying and solving women's problems", it is envisaged to repair women's housing included in the "women's notebook", which is valid precisely for the women's layer in need of social protection.

3.3% of respondents indicated that the main problem was material-spiritual maturity and independence as a person resulting from it. It can be summed up that the basis of the problem is the issue of women's education and employment. As an educated and expert in her field, a woman, as a person, is primarily in constant development in society, she does not have problems finding a place to work, and through this she is able to satisfy her material and spiritual needs. According to the statistics agency official figures, as of July 30, 2023, the population occupied in the economy is 13,538,876, out of which females are 5,595,267 and males are 7,943,609. Women who make up a large part of the population (18,304,675) [7] at the moment are recorded in relatively smaller numbers in this regard. This is primarily due to the fact that the Uzbek mentality is associated with the fact that women should be mainly engaged in child education and household chores, but it is advisable to bring women's activity in society, their financial freedom, to the level of an issue that is always relevant and supported on the side of the population. Since, woman's place as a person

in society, high self-confidence and also has a great influence on the economic development of the state.

The same question was asked to girls aged 15-18 years. “What problem basically do you think is common among girls of your age?” to which they answered as follows:

Figure 2. Opinion of girls' in rural areas.

Girls at this age of their own face mainly psychological problems. This is exactly what 23.3% of respondents claim. That's why so many percent of girls had difficulty answering the question. So, they have a great need for psychological conversations. 20% of participants noted that mainly problems with the norms of etiquette are spreading widely among them. Also, 16.6% of participants have established that early marriage is a big problem for them today. That is to say that today in our society, no matter how many conversations and meetings with parents are organized, the problem of early marriage of girls still accounts for a large percentage. As long as the Code of administrative responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes that the parent who marries a child under the age of marriage is liable. According to it, the granting or domestication of a person under the age of marriage by a parent or their replacement will cause a fine of seven to fifteen times the amount of the base calculation. [8] Also, the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan clearly defines the circumstances in which a forced marriage can be found invalid. [9] But the girls who grew up in the Uzbek environment do not express their displeasure in cases of forced marriage due to the mentality of not going against the will of their parents. This is seen as disrespectful

to the parents. But forced marriage it ends with the fact that the future family will soon divorce, inappropriate situations between the couple and even, in some cases, the suicide of women.

6.6% of girls who are survey participants claim that education is a big problem in front of them. It is said that even at the level of attending school, the most important, irrevocable general secondary education, they are facing problems. First of all, every mother should ask herself the question of how the future mothers of the society can be deprived of general secondary education and become good role models and educators for their children in the future. 6.6% of girls say that not being able to set the right goal at this age has become a major problem among their peers. 15-18 years is a period of determining goals for the future, developing future plans, clearly defining a profession, direction. The fact that 6.6% of our girls are in trouble in this matter during this period is a sign that they have a high need for psychological training and conversations. The fact that the above 16.6% of girls are tormented by psychological problems is also directly related to the issue of making decisions, setting serious goals.

According to the survey, most of the problems reported by women are employment and financial stability and the right to choose. The education of women and girls, becoming a specialist in a certain field, and having a permanent job will provide them with both mental peace and financial freedom.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, in solving the problems related to women, joint cooperation of the general public and law promotion bodies is necessary. Studying it in sufficient scientific and practical detail, Society should understand that violence against women is violence against humanity. Because women are physically and mentally fragile due to biological reasons. They should be protected from violence and abuse.

Based on the above problems, the following recommendations can be made:

- increase the legal knowledge of women. To give them a detailed understanding of where they first turn when harassment or violence is used, where their information

is protected by legislation when they apply, how to provide assistance to the affected women;

- women in critical condition are served by the Republican Center for the rehabilitation and adaptation of women under the Ministry of neighborhood and family support, it can be contacted through the only single number throughout the Republic – 1146, victimized women can apply for issues that afflict them every day, as well as the development of the "Salvation" application by the center and;

- women's policy framework continuous support of women subjected to harassment and violence until they stand on their feet socioeconomically;

- to establish a system of access and readability to families of guidelines under development for the rehabilitation of abused and repressed women.

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